

Modeling of Liquid Fuel Thermal Axial Expansion in Static Liquid Fuel Reactors with Dragon/Donjon Version 5

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ABSTRACT

Static Liquid Fuel Reactors (SLFRs) offer unique safety and performance features among Small Modular Reactor (SMR) concepts, notably a strong negative temperature coefficient via liquid fuel density changes. However, accurately modeling the coupled neutronic, thermal-hydraulic, and geometric feedbacks—especially thermal axial expansion of the liquid fuel—remains a challenge. This work presents new developments in the Donjon Version 5 code, including a dedicated module for liquid fuel thermal axial expansion (LFTAE) and improved treatment of molten salt properties and heat transfer. Initial verification against high-fidelity CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) code OpenFOAM demonstrates that the enhanced Donjon/Dragon suite may be used to simulate SLFR behavior with results consistent with the physics behind this phenomena confirming the suitability of the approach for advanced SLFR design and analysis. Future work will address further verification and transient scenarios.

Keywords: static liquid fuel reactor, molten salt, thermal axial expansion

1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are at the forefront of next-generation nuclear technology, with over 80 commercial designs in development worldwide [1]. Among these, Static Liquid Fuel Reactors (SLFRs) are of particular interest due to the complex feedbacks between fuel temperature, density, and geometry. This concept, initially developed in the 60s using aqueous solutions [2] and liquid metal fuel [3], and revisited recently by the Moltex Energy team using molten salts[4][5], relies on unpumped liquid fuel contained within tubes. This configuration enables a rapid, negative temperature coefficient of reactivity by changes in the fuel density, enhancing inherent safety. However, the fuel temperature profile in the core due to radial tube location and/or presence of control rod or neutron absorbers, results in a different fuel height due to the thermal axial expansion of the liquid fuel in the tubes.

Accurate simulation of SLFRs requires coupled modeling of neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and evolving fuel geometry. Existing reactor physics codes, such as Dragon and Donjon, were originally developed for solid-fuel systems and require significant adaptation for SLFR applications. In particular, modeling the thermal axial expansion of static liquid fuel is essential for capturing feedback effects and optimizing reactor performance.

This paper presents recent developments in the Donjon Version 5 code, including a new module for liquid fuel thermal axial expansion (LFTAE) and improved treatment of molten salt properties and heat transfer in the existing thermal-hydraulics module (THM). Preliminary verification is conducted through a series of case studies, ranging from single-physics thermal-hydraulics to fully coupled multi-physics simulations, demonstrating the feasibility of using LFTAE for modelling of thermal axial expansion in SLFRs.

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2. COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS AND MODEL IMPROVEMENTS

The Version 5 project comprises a suite of reactor physics codes developed at École Polytechnique de Montréal, including Dragon (lattice code), Trivac (full-core neutron flux solver), and Donjon (full-core operation code including control rod movement, refueling and simplified thermal-hydraulics)[6] originally targeting PWR, CANDU, and Advanced CANDU (ACR) reactors with solid fuel.

In Donjon multi-physics simulations are performed by coupling the neutronics and power solver modules (FLU and POW) with the simplified thermal-hydraulics module (THM) [7]. In THM, the reactor core geometry is modeled as a series of parallel coolant channels with no cross-flow that are heated by cylindrical fuel rods with constant radius along the axial length, whose power in a multi-physics calculation is obtained from the neutronic solution. In the axial direction, each channel is discretized using a finite volume discretization along 1D axial nodes. In the radial direction, for each axial node, the temperature distribution in the fuel rod and cladding is modeled using the 1D Fourier's law of heat conduction in radial coordinates with a mesh-centered finite difference discretization in which the radial mesh is defined so that each control volume has a constant lateral surface area within the fuel rod. The heat transfer between clad and coolant is modeled using empirical correlations that account for different flow regimes. In the single-phase regime, the forced convective heat transfer is described by the Dittus-Boelter correlation. This correlation, despite its remarkable usefulness for water, may result in large errors when used with molten salts [8].

The THM module was extended to enable heat transfer modeling in SLFRs. Key improvements include:

1. **Molten Salt Properties:** Integration of a curated database for retrieval of molten salt thermophysical properties from the Molten Salt Thermophysical Properties Database (MSTDB-TP), reviewed and maintained by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL)[9].
2. **Heat Transfer Correlations:** Implementation of the Gnielinski correlation [10] for forced convection in molten salt coolants, replacing the Dittus-Boelter correlation used for water.
3. **Fuel-Cladding Interface:** New routines for direct contact between liquid fuel and cladding, omitting the gap term.
4. **Fuel Heat Transfer:** Adaptation of conduction equations for liquid fuel, neglecting natural convection as a first approximation.

3. LIQUID FUEL THERMAL AXIAL EXPANSION (LFTAE) MODEL

In SLFRs, temperature-induced volumetric expansion of the liquid fuel causes the fuel level within the tube to rise. The approach followed in the LFTAE model consists on the discretization of the axial length of the fuel tubes into Z nodes ($N_i, i \in (0, Z)$), the first L nodes are fully filled with fuel, while the remaining $Z - L$, are empty, as depicted in Figure 1.

A scalar field representing the volume fraction of liquid fuel, α_i , in a given node can be introduced. The volume fraction takes the value of 1 in the L nodes fully filled with fuel, and 0 in the $Z - L$ empty. After an increase in temperature the liquid fuel salt will expand inside the tube reaching a new height, H' , and the node $L + 1$ will start filling of liquid fuel to height $\delta h = H' - H$.

The value of α_{L+1} can be obtained by considering the conservation of fuel mass inside the tube, m_t . For uniform axial discretization ($h_i = \Delta H$) and considering that the radius is constant along the tube and has a surface area S_R , the volume fraction in the last partially filled node is:

$$\alpha_{L+1} = \frac{1}{\rho_{L+1}} \left[\frac{m_t}{S_R \Delta H} - \sum_{i=1}^L \rho_i \right] \quad (1)$$

Where ρ_i is the density of the fuel at node i and ρ_{L+1} is the density of the fuel in the last partially

Figure 1. Axial discretization for LFTAE modeling.

filled node $L + 1$. Nodes with $\alpha_i = 0$ have no fuel (produce no power) and are excluded from the heat transfer calculations. Nodes with $0 < \alpha_i < 1$ are partially filled and therefore only a portion of the node produces power.

The LFTAE module updates the fuel volume fraction distribution based on local temperatures and densities, ensuring mass conservation in each tube. For convergence check, the module calculates the maximum relative fuel height variation between two iterations in all channels, stopping when it is below a given percentage.

From the neutronics point of view, the homogenized cross sections are generated using DRAGON for the central pin of a 3x3 pin configuration. The cross sections are obtained for different combinations of the conventional parameters in coupled simulations (e.g. fuel and coolant temperatures) as well as the volume fraction in the central pin, allowing for partially filled nodes in the full core simulation. These cross sections are compiled in the reactor database that is then interpolated in Donjon to obtain the neutronics solution and the system's power distribution.

Figure 2. Multi-physics coupling scheme.

By including the LFTAE module in the coupling scheme, as shown in Figure 2, an update in the fuel temperature distribution caused by a change in the power distribution will produce a change in the fuel volume fraction, effectively capturing geometrical changes due to axial thermal expansion of the fuel.

It must be noted that, since THM assumes constant radius along the axial length, this model neglects the variation of the fuel tube radius with temperature (radial thermal expansion). By comparing the linear thermal expansion coefficient of the tube (steel or other alloy) with the volumetric thermal expansion coefficient of the liquid fuel (molten salt), it can be shown that this simplification is valid when the height of the fuel salt inside the tube is between 30 to 90 times the radius of the tube, depending on the specific fuel salt and tube material. While in most cases this condition is accomplished, as the radius of the tube is typically in the order of centimeters and the height of meters, attention must be paid when using this approach in smaller cores with reduced height.

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND VERIFICATION

To develop and evaluate the newly implemented capabilities, a series of simplified case studies were designed to model various aspects of SLFRs. It is important to emphasize that these case studies are not intended to represent actual SLFR systems. Instead, they serve as controlled environments for testing and verification purposes. Consequently, considerations such as manufacturability, material compatibility, and engineering feasibility are intentionally excluded.

4.1. CS-01: Molten Salt Thermal-Hydraulics

The first case study, CS-01, focuses on validating the heat transfer capabilities for molten salt fuel and coolant. The model consists of a single fuel tube (0.9 cm of inner diameter, 0.1 cm thick Zircalloy cladding) embedded in a Cartesian lattice with a pitch of 1.26 cm and reflective boundary conditions. The channel has a total height of 1.5 m, with 1 m filled with liquid fuel.

The fuel is assumed to exhibit the thermo-physical properties of $LiF - BeF_2$ (66–34 mol%), while the coolant corresponds to $LiF - NaF - KF$ (46.5–11.5–42 mol%), both of which are well-characterized molten salt systems with data sourced from MSTDB-TP. The coolant enters the system at 800 K with a velocity of 3 m/s.

A thermal-hydraulics model was developed in Donjon using the THM module, discretizing the channel into 10 axial nodes. The THM module was benchmarked against OpenFOAM [11] CFD simulations using the conjugate heat transfer solver [12] and $k-\omega$ turbulence modeling [13]. To enable comparison, temperature distributions from OpenFOAM were averaged over the Donjon axial mesh to produce node-averaged values.

Figure 3. Coolant Temperature Profile.

Figure 4. Fuel Temperature Profile.

Figures 3 and 4 show the axial average temperature profiles and the relative deviation of the coolant and fuel respectively, for the case with a power density of 500 kW/l. As it can be seen, for the coolant temperature profile, the deviations are below 2% over the axial length. However, the deviations on the average fuel temperature are slightly higher, nevertheless, remaining below 10% over the axial length. The changes in slopes of the OpenFOAM solution in the first nodes seen in both Figures can be explained by the inlet thermal and hydrodynamic effects that are only captured in the CFD solution.

The axial temperature profiles were compared for different values of fuel power density in the system, ranging from 25 kW/l to 2 MW/l. While the differences on the average coolant temperature remain below 10% in all cases, in some cases with very high power density, the differences in the average fuel temperature reach up to 30%.

A possible explanation of this behavior can be the effect of natural convection in the liquid fuel as well as conduction in the axial direction. The OpenFOAM solution is considering this effect, while the Donjon solution is not.

All in all, considering the accuracy of the Gnielinski correlation, the capability of the THM module to simulate heat transfer in liquid fuel and coolant systems can be considered with sufficient fidelity for reactor-scale analysis. Further future improvements, such as the introduction of natural convection models in THM and the improvement of the OpenFOAM models to remove the inlet effects, may reduce further the deviations found.

4.2. CS-02: Partial Multi-Physics Model (TH+TE)

The second case study, CS-02, evaluates the coupling between the thermal-hydraulics (THM) and liquid fuel thermal axial expansion (LFTAE) modules. The system comprises a 5x5 lattice of channels, each identical in geometry and material properties to those in CS-01.

The radial power profile shown in Figure 5 is imposed across the lattice, introducing a radial asymmetry, with varying power outputs among channels. This configuration mimics the radial power distribution observed in SLFRs due to factors such as channel positioning, fuel burnup, enrichment variations, and localized neutron absorbers. The convergence criteria in LFTAE was set to 0.01% so the calculation stops when the relative fuel height difference between two iterations in any of the pins is below 0.015 cm.

The coupling between the THM and LFTAE modules was tested under the non-uniform radial power distribution. The solution of the coupled system converged in 12 iterations showing that the thermal expansion effects are strongly dependent on the local power density, with channels producing higher power exhibiting greater axial elongation, with differences in the channel fuel height reaching up to 8 cm (7%) as can be seen in Figure 6.

The LFTAE module successfully captured the axial thermal expansion across the lattice, demonstrating its ability to model the effects of the power distribution on the geometry. These results are essential for future studies involving reactivity feedback and stability in SLFRs.

4.3. CS-03: Full Multi-Physics Model (NK+TH+TE)

The third case study, CS-03, integrates the neutronics solution with the thermal-hydraulics and thermal expansion models, forming a fully coupled multi-physics simulation, as depicted previously in Figure 2. The system also consists of a 5x5 lattice of channels, however this time with a pitch of 1.14 cm and a height of 200 cm to have a critical system. Neutronic calculations are performed using the FLU and POW modules of Donjon Version 5. The convergence criteria in LFTAE was set to 0.01%.

Prior to simulation, homogenized macroscopic cross sections are generated using Dragon. These cross sections are obtained for the central pin, whose fuel level is varied, in a 3x3 lattice. Other cross section parameters considered in the generation of the reactor database are the fuel and coolant temperatures.

Figure 5. Imposed Radial Power Profile (Normalized Values).

Figure 6. Final fuel height in each channel (cm).

Data sets were generated for two enrichment levels: 5% (central pin) and 95% (surrounding pins). This stark contrast induces a radial power profile, with the central pin exhibiting lower power than its neighbors. Although the configuration does not reflect a commercial SLFR, it provides a framework for further development of Donjon with the aim of modeling SLFR systems.

As shown in Figure 7 the coupled system converged in 15 iterations and the effects of the channel height on the neutronic solution were observed through changes in the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}). As seen in Figure 8, the power distribution obtained from the FLU and POW modules showed a clear radial gradient due to the enrichment difference, with the central pin (2-2) exhibiting lower power than the surrounding pins. The parametrized cross sections generated with Dragon allowed accurate modeling of temperature and fuel level dependencies, including partially filled nodes.

Figure 7. Evolution of the effective multiplication factor during iterations.

Figure 8. Node-wise power distribution (kW).

The thermal expansion results were consistent with the power profile, with the central channel having 12 nodes with fuel and the surrounding channels having 14 nodes with fuel (with the last node partially

filled in both cases), resulting in a fuel height difference of about 10 cm, as seen in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9. Final fuel height in each channel (cm).

Figure 10. Node-wise fuel volume fraction (α_i) distribution.

Overall, the results confirm the suitability of the methodology, and the newly implemented modules in Donjon, for modeling advanced SLFR concepts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the development and initial verification of new modeling capabilities for Static Liquid Fuel Reactors (SLFRs) within the Dragon and Donjon code systems. Through a series of progressively complex case studies, the individual and coupled behavior of thermal-hydraulics, thermal expansion, and neutronics phenomena were investigated.

The first case study (CS-01) demonstrated the newly implemented thermal-hydraulics module (THM) for molten salt systems, showing sufficient fidelity for reactor-scale analysis. The second case study (CS-02) coupled thermal-hydraulics and liquid fuel thermal axial expansion (LFTAE), highlighting the sensitivity of expansion effects to radial power distributions. The third case study (CS-03) integrated all modules into a fully coupled multi-physics simulation, successfully capturing the feedback mechanisms between power distribution, temperature, and geometry.

The results are consistent with the physics behind these phenomena and confirm that the extended capabilities of Dragon and Donjon may be suitable for modeling advanced SLFR concepts, including systems with complex feedback interactions. The LFTAE module can effectively capture geometric and reactivity changes due to thermal axial expansion.

Future work will focus on further verification by comparing CS-02 and CS-03 to coupled neutronics-CFD solutions and extending the capabilities to transient simulations as well as the investigation of the reactivity feedbacks introduced by the thermal expansion of the liquid fuel and the investigation of the role of radiative heat transfer in SLFRs.

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